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An Analysis of Health and Safety Provisions in the NEC Contracts.

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34 **ABSTRACT**

35

36 The 2015 edition of the CDM Regulations impose statutory duties on the project client
37 and other project supply chain members. It is the client's statutory duty to make and
38 implement arrangements for effective management of health and safety (H&S) on the
39 project. They also created two statutory duty holders that the client must appoint to
40 coordinate H&S management. To manage the performance of the duty holders
41 effectively, the client must enter into a contract with each of them that imposes their
42 statutory duties as contractual obligations. The paper critically analyses two
43 representative contracts in the NEC family of contracts to provide guidance on their
44 H&S provisions and pointers to possible review in future editions. An important finding
45 is that the contracts state the H&S duties in very general terms with the expectation that
46 users will draft the details on the CDM duties as part of the Scope contract document.
47 This approach has the advantage of flexibility to accommodate international use of the
48 contracts. It is recommended that the promoters consider the alternative of capturing
49 appropriate CDM related duties as a standard optional clause for adoption by UK users.
50 Suggestions are made as to the terms in such an optional clause.

51

52 **Keywords**

53 Contracts & Law, Health & Safety, Project Management

54

55 **INTRODUCTION**

56

57 The primary UK domestic legislation relevant to health and safety (H&S) at work is the
58 Health and Safety at Work Act 1974 (HASAWA) which applies across industries. This
59 Act sets out the framework of the law on H&S at work and provides mechanisms for
60 enforcing compliance with it. Contravention of any H&S duties under the Act is a
61 criminal offence under s. 33(1) (c) and, as such, liable to prosecution. S. 15 of the Act
62 authorises the Secretary of State (a senior Minister of the Government) for the
63 appropriate government department to make ‘H&S Regulations’ applicable to specific
64 industries and H&S risks that become part of the Act. Many Regulations on specific
65 aspects of H&S risks in the construction industry have been passed and carry effect as
66 provided for under HASAWA.

67

68 Much of the UK H&S law emanated from membership of the European Union (EU).
69 EU H&S law in the form of Directive 1992/57/EEC was first implemented as UK law
70 on 31 March 1995 as the Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 1994
71 (CDM 1994). They placed specific statutory duties on the traditional project participants
72 (clients, contractors and designers). They also created two new duty holders labelled
73 “Planning Supervisor” and “Principal Contractor” for the coordination of H&S matters
74 at the pre-construction and construction phases, respectively, of projects. As the
75 industry grew in experience of the operation of CDM 1994 on construction sites,
76 criticism of various aspects of the Regulations emerged. In response, CDM 1994 were
77 replaced with the Construction (Design and Management) Regulations 2007 (CDM
78 2007). CDM 2007 were in turn replaced by the Construction (Design and Management)
79 Regulations 2015 (CDM 2015), which came into force on 6 April 2015. The changes

80 made included relabelling of what was originally the Planning Supervisor as the
81 Principal Designer.

82

83 The basis of statutory duty under the Regulations is the simple fact of being a CDM
84 duty holder, which is sufficient to impose the relevant duty on the duty holder with
85 accompanying criminal liability for non-compliance. They are of direct application in
86 the sense that very little contractual formality is required for the application of the
87 obligations under the Regulations to a duty holder. The only contractual requirement is
88 that the Principal Designer (PD) and the Principal Contractor (PC) should be appointed
89 in writing by the Client. However, for at least two main reasons, the CDM Client needs
90 to pay particular attention to the content of the contracts by which it procures the
91 services of the duty holders. The first reason stems from the Client's duty under
92 Regulation 4(1) not only to make suitable arrangements for managing H&S on the
93 project but also to ensure that the arrangements are maintained and reviewed throughout
94 the duration of the project. Regulation 4(6) requires the Client to go further and take
95 reasonable steps to ensure that the CDM duty holders comply with their duties. There is
96 therefore the obvious implication that the management arrangements must be monitored
97 to assess whether they are having the desired effect and to take appropriate remedial
98 action. Whilst the Health and Safety Executive (HSE), the designated state authority,
99 may prosecute any duty holder for breach of the Regulations, appropriate contracts with
100 duty holders provide the Client with the only lever for enforcing their compliance with
101 the Regulations. The Client must therefore not only establish a contractual relationship
102 with each CDM duty holder in relation to its statutory duty but also ensure the
103 cascading of those contractual liabilities throughout the contractual chains linking the
104 supply chain members.

105

106 The second reason concerns the Client's self-interest. Breach of duty by a duty holder
107 would often result in the Client's criminal liability from which the Client stands to
108 suffer not only direct financial loss in costs of legal advice and representation and fines
109 (or even imprisonment in the case of human clients) but also reputational damage.
110 Further, the CDM Client is open to wider risks of financial loss from personal injury,
111 death of workpeople on the site or members of the general public, property damage and
112 project delays and disruption caused by breach of duty under the Regulations.
113 Regarding the risks of personal injury, death or property damage, it is for each victim or
114 their personal representatives to determine whom to hold responsible for the harm
115 suffered. The usual reaction of anybody injured or who suffers damage to its property is
116 to sue whoever is perceived causally responsible, either in part or wholly, for the injury
117 or damage. The most visible targets include the Client or any of the CDM duty holders
118 prominently identified in signs and notices on the project. The main legal grounds on
119 which liability may attach to the Client include negligence, nuisance, trespass, strict
120 liability and liability under *Rylands v Fletcher* principle.

121

122 In deciding whom to sue for injury or loss, the strategy of the typical claimant is often
123 that of the proverbial 'duck shoot' or the so-called 'scatter gun' approach, i.e. the victim
124 sues everybody involved on the site (Ndekugri and Rycroft, 2009). The Client may
125 therefore be sued for events flowing from a breach of the Regulations by any of the duty
126 holders. Such suit may occasion financial loss to the Client even where it successfully
127 defends the victim's claim. Self-interest mandates a contractual relationship through
128 which such loss can be passed on to the relevant duty breaker. Contracts therefore have
129 risk clauses that seek to specify, as between the duty holder and the CDM Client, which

130 contractual party will be responsible for which risk. Risk clauses are often accompanied
131 with indemnity clauses stating that where one party suffers financial loss from a risk for
132 which the other is responsible, the latter should indemnify the former.

133

134 A “contractor”, which is defined to include not only main contractors but also sub-
135 contractors, is required by Regulation 15(3) to comply with any direction of the PD and
136 the PC. Such direction may not only create variations to the works but also cause delay
137 and disruption to them. One of the challenges of such intervention by the PD or the PC
138 is avoidance of disturbance to the governance system of contract management giving
139 contract administrators sole authority for issuing instructions to the main contractor.

140 There is therefore a need to address these issues in the main contract and contracts of
141 engagement of duty holders. For example, should the main contractor be entitled to
142 extension of time or financial compensation for delay and disruption caused by a
143 direction from the PD or PC? If there is such entitlement, the liability should be passed
144 to the duty holder who caused the delay or disruption through terms in the relevant
145 contract of engagement.

146

147 A Client’s strategy for compliance with its CDM duties must therefore include engaging
148 the duty holders through contracts with appropriate content. Accordingly, drafting
149 committees for the construction industry’s standard form contracts revised them to take
150 account of the original CDM Regulations and, thereafter, their revisions. A review of
151 the extant literature, summarised in the paper, found very little on CDM related
152 provisions in standard form contracts. This paper reports on research into provisions on
153 H&S generally and CDM 2015 in particular in two representative members of the NEC
154 family of standard form contracts: the NEC4 Engineering and Construction Contract

155 (NEC4 ECC) (NEC, 2017a) and the NEC4 Professional Services Contract (NEC,
156 2017d). It is intended primarily to provide guidance to users of the contracts on how
157 H&S risks can be effectively addressed in their preparation of the documents required
158 by the contract. It is also hoped that it will inform the producers of the contracts in
159 future contract reviews. The paper is structured in nine parts as follows. Section 2
160 outlines the methods followed in carrying out the research on which the paper is based.
161 The review of the relevant literature is summarised in Section 3. Section 4 identifies the
162 duty holders under the Regulations and examines the nature of their duties. The
163 Regulations require the preparation of certain documents in the management of H&S.
164 Section 5 identifies these documents and examines their content requirements. The
165 relevant contractual provisions in the NEC4 ECC and NEC4 PSC are analysed in
166 Sections 6 and 7, respectively. Conclusions are drawn after a brief discussion in Section
167 8.

168

169 **2 RESEARCH METHOD**

170

171 The research on which the paper is based was carried out in two parts with some
172 iteration between them. Firstly, the CDM 2015 Regulations were analysed using
173 principles of statutory interpretation as described typically by Bailey and Norbury
174 (2017) and Bell and Engle (1994). One of these principles, referred to as the “literal
175 rule”, is that a statutory provision is to be interpreted using the ordinary meaning of the
176 words used in it except where the words or terms are defined in the statute or the literal
177 meaning is absurd. For example, “designer” and “contractor” are defined under the
178 Regulations giving them meanings different from their ordinary usage and were treated
179 accordingly. There are other rules of statutory interpretation for use where application

180 of the literal rule is inappropriate but they were not found to be relevant here because of
181 the opportunities taken to eliminate problems of interpretation in the successive
182 revisions of the Regulations.

183

184 The standard form contracts were then scrutinised with the aim of identifying terms
185 relevant to the Regulations and working out their meanings by the application of the
186 principles governing the interpretation of contracts distilled from case law, such as
187 *Investors Compensation Scheme Ltd v West Bromwich Building Society* [1998] 1 WLR
188 896; *Chartbrook Ltd v Persimmon Homes Ltd* [2009] UKHL 38; *Arnold v Britton*
189 [2015] UKSC 36 and *Rainy Sky SA v Kookmin Bank* [2011] UKSC 50, and captured in
190 textbooks such as Lewison (2015). Account was also taken of the further guidance
191 provided by the Supreme Court in *Wood v Capita Insurance Services Ltd* [2017] UKSC
192 24 on the approach to contractual interpretation, particularly the interpretation of
193 indemnity clauses, which are in the contracts in this paper.

194

195 **3 SUMMARY OF LITERATURE REVIEW**

196

197 The extant literature on the CDM regulations falls into broad two categories. The first
198 category is a combination of: expert commentaries on the letter of the legislation;
199 practitioner commentaries based on individual experience of the implementation of the
200 Regulations into practice; and reports of surveys into industry views on their experience
201 of the Regulations in practice. Most of these publications, which are summarised in
202 Table A, were on the 1994 and 2007 editions of the Regulations and were aimed at
203 identifying shortcomings in the Regulations for improvement action by construction

204 industry businesses or review of the Regulations by the HSE. The main shortcomings
205 identified were:

- 206 • late appointments of duty holders by clients;
- 207 • duty holder general competence deficits;
- 208 • overly bureaucratic practices;
- 209 • generation of excessive and irrelevant paperwork to maximise protection in the
210 event of prosecution; misunderstanding of the Regulations;
- 211 • ambiguities in the responsibilities of duty holders;
- 212 • lack of relevant training and supervision;
- 213 • misunderstanding of the CDM roles;
- 214 • inappropriate industry practice and norms; inadequate levels of prosecutions;
- 215 • lack of awareness of the Regulations;
- 216 • inadequate management of risk at the pre-construction stage; and
- 217 • inadequate leadership of compliance with the Regulations.

218

219 [Table A about here]

220

221 The second category of literature concerned analysis of provisions implementing the
222 Regulations into contracts within project supply chains. Apart from overviews of CDM
223 related provisions in the industry's standard form contracts in some textbooks (e.g.,
224 Ndekugri and Rycroft, 2009; Broome, 2012; Rowlinson, 2018; Eggleston, 2019), the
225 review found very little in this category. The review uncovered only two publications
226 based on the 2007 edition of the Regulations (Mzyece *et al*, 2012; Patterson *et al*, 2015)
227 whilst the little research literature on aspects of CDM 2015 (e.g., Manu *et al.*, 2017;
228 Manu *et al.*, 2019; Poghosyan *et al*, 2020; ICE, 2020) hardly considers contractual

229 content, thus confirming the need for analysis of provisions implementing the
230 Regulation into supply chain contracts.

231

232 **4 DUTY HOLDERS AND THEIR DUTIES UNDER THE REGULATIONS**

233

234 In relation to a construction project the Regulations specify certain statutory duty
235 holders: a CDM Client, a Principal Designer; designers, a Principal Contractor, and
236 contractors. Designers and contractors (including sub-contractors at all levels) must
237 have the skills, knowledge, and experience (SKE) and, if an organisation, the
238 organisational capability (OC) necessary for effective management of H&S (Regulation
239 8(1)). Any party responsible for appointing a designer or a contractor must take
240 reasonable steps to satisfy themselves that the appointee possesses these attributes
241 whilst a candidate for appointment must not accept it unless they meet these
242 requirements. Detailed understanding of the roles and the related statutory duties can be
243 developed by reading the Regulations in the light of published commentaries (Bussey,
244 2015; Joyce, 2015; Putsman and McArthur, 2015).

245

246 **5 CDM DOCUMENTS**

247

248 The Regulations mandate the preparation and sharing of certain information by
249 specified duty holders. Regulation 9(4) puts on a designer, as defined in the
250 Regulations, a duty to take “all reasonable steps to provide, with the design, sufficient
251 information about the design, construction or maintenance of the structure”. The
252 information to be provided must adequately assist other duty holders to comply with
253 their duties under the Regulations. There is an express requirement to provide to the PD

254 information on risks not eliminated by the design and other appropriate information for
255 the Health and Safty File (HSF). There is no express duty to provide the information
256 directly to other duty holders. Other documents to be prepared and shared are: pre-
257 construction information (PCI); construction phase plan (CPP); and the health and
258 safety file (HSF).

259

260 The PCI is information in the Client’s possession or reasonably obtainable by or on
261 behalf the Client concerning: the project; the planning and management of the project;
262 and H&S hazards on the site or hazards associated with the design and construction of
263 the project. Appendix 2 to the HSE guidance document on the Regulations (HSE, 2015)
264 sets out the content requirements of the PCI and actions required of other duty holders
265 in relation the preparation, review and use of the documents whilst Appendix 5 explains
266 how it interacts with the other CDM documents on multi-contractor projects. The CPP
267 is defined as “a plan drawn up under Regulation 12 or 15”. Regulation 12(1) puts on
268 the Principal Contractor on a multi-contractor project a duty to prepare the CPP during
269 the pre-construction phase or to arrange for it to be prepared. On a single contractor site,
270 this duty is on the contractor (Regulation 15(5)). The Client must ensure that the CPP is
271 prepared before the construction phase begins (Regulation 4(5)). Its contents, as
272 summarised in Regulation 12(2), include the H&S management arrangements and site
273 rules governing the carrying out of construction work on the site. It must also include
274 specific measures on particular risks listed in Schedule 3 to the Regulations, e.g, risk of
275 burial by failure of excavations, power lines, and the installation or dismantling of
276 heavy pre-fabricated structures. Regulation 12(5) puts on the PD the duty to prepare the
277 HSF. It must include information relating to the project likely to be needed to ensure the

278 H&S of any person involved on any subsequent project, e.g, maintenance, extension, or
279 demolition of the structure resulting from the prior project.

280

281 **6 NEC4 ENGINEERING AND CONSTRUCTION CONTRACT**

282

283 The study of this contract identified the following as its constituent contract documents:
284 Form of Agreement; Contract Data; Scope; Site Information; Bill of Quantities/Activity
285 Schedule; and conditions of contract (NEC, 2017b).

286

287 No standard Form of Agreement is provided as part of the book commonly referred to
288 as the NEC4 ECC although a sample contract agreement is provided as part of the
289 NEC4 User Guide (NEC, 2017c). The expectation of the sponsors of the contract on this
290 subject appears to be that a bespoke contract agreement can be created by an exchange
291 of letters between the Client and Contractor creating a contractual relationship on the
292 basis of the Contract Data and the other contract documents incorporated by it. It would
293 appear that the drafters of the NEC4 ECC took a view that parties are more likely to
294 prefer using their own in-house standard contract agreements to using any specified
295 standard form imposed as part of the contract. However, a sample contract agreement is
296 provided as part of the NEC4 User Guide (NEC, 2017c).

297

298 The Contract Data, which is in two parts, sets out the information on the particular
299 project without which the Conditions of Contract cannot be operated. Contract Data part
300 one is compiled by the Client and issued to tenderers as part of the tender documents.
301 Tenderers complete the Contract Data part two template and return it as part of their

302 tenders. Finally, it identifies (by document title or reference number) the other contract
303 documents.

304

305 The Scope describes the works to be provided by the Contractor within specified
306 constraints. The equivalent document under the predecessor of the NEC4 ECC was
307 referred to as the “Works Information”. The Scope usually comprises multiple disparate
308 documents, e.g., drawings and a traditional specification. The expectation is that the
309 identities of the documents forming part of the Scope are entered in appropriate parts of
310 the Contract Data. Information in any Project Manager’s instruction under the contract
311 adding to or modifying the specification or description of the works or the constraints
312 within which they are to be carried out becomes part of the Scope.

313

314 Site Information is defined by Clause 11.2(18) as “information which describes the Site
315 and its surroundings”. The identifiers of the documents in which this information is to
316 be found are to be completed in the Contract Data part one. Types of information to be
317 provided as part of Site Information include: information from subsoil investigations
318 carried out; information on buildings and other structures on the Site; information on
319 services at, on or adjacent to the Site; and reports of any special investigation
320 commissioned by the Client such as asbestos surveys and hydrographic surveys.

321

322 The conditions of contract are the detailed terms governing the performance of the
323 contract. A distinction of this contract is that, unlike all other standard form contracts, it
324 does not provide a set of terms that apply to all projects which it is used to procure.
325 Instead, it has a set of core clauses that apply to all projects on which it is used. There
326 are then three levels of options: a choice of one from six main options according to the

327 payment approach adopted for the project; choice of any number from 25 secondary
328 options (Options X1-X22; Options Y(UK) 1,2 and 3) to suit the user's procurement
329 decisions and related statutory provisions; and a choice of one from three dispute
330 resolution options. The conditions of contract make only three specific references to
331 H&S: the Contractor's obligation under Clauses 20.1 and 27.4 to act in accordance with
332 the H&S requirements stated in the Scope; the Contractor's duty under Clause 31.2 to
333 show on each programme submitted "provisions for health and safety requirements";
334 and contract termination provisions in Clause 90.1 and 91.3. There are other provisions
335 that can be operated to promote H&S generally and to ensure compliance with the
336 Regulations although neither the CDM Regulations nor H&S generally is mentioned in
337 them. They include: the requirement in Clause 10.2; the early warning procedures under
338 Clause 15; risk allocation provisions in Clauses 81.1 and 82.1; and early contractor
339 involvement under Option X22.

340

341 **6.1 Obligations under Clauses 20.1 and 27.4**

342

343 Clause 20.1 states the Contractor's primary obligation to provide the works in
344 accordance with the Scope. As part of this general obligation, the Contractor is required
345 by Clause 27.4 to act in accordance "the health and safety requirements stated in the
346 Scope". Any important H&S requirement or constrain must therefore be clearly stated
347 in the Scope. This provision links in with the definition of "Completion" under Clause
348 11.2(2) as "when the Contractor has done all the work which the Scope states is to be
349 done by the Completion Date and corrected notified Defects which would have
350 prevented the Client from using the works or Others from doing their work". If no
351 specific conditions are stated in the Scope, the test of Completion is "when the

352 Contractor has done all the work necessary for the Client to use the works and for
353 Others to do their work”. This accords with the definition of “practical completion” in
354 the common law, which is reviewed in
355 *Mears Ltd v Costplan Services (South East) Ltd* [2019] EWCA Civ 502;[2019] BLR
356 289. As the Contractor has the highest possible motivation to have the works declared
357 complete by the Project Manager when it believes it has carried out all the works to
358 physical completion, there is a strong case for imposing specific H&S safety outcomes
359 as pre-conditions for Completion. Examples include: providing all relevant H&S
360 information to not only the Client but also other duty holders who may need such
361 information for the completion of their H&S duties.

362

363 There is an independent statutory obligation to comply with all applicable legislation,
364 including the CDM 2015 in the sense that, without this clause, the Contractor still has to
365 comply with the legislation. The real effect of Clause 27.4, if the Scope expressly
366 requires the Contractor’s compliance with the Regulations, is to impose compliance
367 with the Regulations as contractual obligations. Such contractual provision allows the
368 Client to claim, as damages for breach of contract, its losses suffered as a consequence
369 of the Contractor’s breach of the Regulations. Depending on the content of the Scope,
370 the Contractor may assume duties beyond the bare requirements of the Regulations. For
371 example, it may specify the level and quality of the staff resources that the Contractor
372 should provide and the powers of the Client and the Project Manager to intervene if the
373 Contractor is failing in some aspects of its H&S duties. Unfortunately, there is no
374 equivalent of Clause 27.4 creating a contractual obligation on the Client to comply with
375 the Regulations. Contractual obligations on the Client spelling out how the statutory

376 duty is complied with provide a route through which the Contractor may recover
377 damages consequent on the breach of the statutory duty.

378

379 **6.2 Obligations under Clause 31.2**

380

381 Clause 31.2 requires the Contractor to show on each programme submitted “provisions
382 for health and safety requirements”. Matters that can be shown on a programme are
383 either operations or events. The Regulations themselves only identify the duties of the
384 Contractor. This clause will have any practical effect only if specific activities (e.g.,
385 preparation of the CPP or HSF) or events (e.g., submission of updated CPPs) within
386 these duties are identified in the Scope, which may also require the programme to
387 include a schedule of H&S information to be submitted (NEC, 2017b, p. 64).

388

389 **6.3 Termination under Clause 91.1 and 91.3**

390

391 The third specific provision is in Clauses 90.1 and 91.3. Under the latter clause, the
392 Project Manager may serve a notice of a default if the Contractor has “substantially
393 broken a health and safety regulation”. If, after the notice, the Contractor has not
394 stopped the default within four weeks, the Client may terminate the Contractor’s
395 employment. To exercise the right to terminate, the Client must serve notice to the
396 Project Manager under Clause 90.1 citing the failure to remedy the H&S breach as the
397 reason for its intention to terminate the contract. The termination takes effect upon the
398 Project Manager responding to the Client’s notice with the issue of a termination
399 certificate. There is no express corresponding right of the Contractor to terminate for
400 the Client’s breach of its H&S duties.

401

402 **6.4 Clause 10.2**

403

404 Cooperation and coordination within the project supply chain constitute a hub of the
405 Regulations (for example, see Regulations 8(4),11(5), 13(2), and 13(5)) and echoes the
406 supply chain integration ethos articulated in general project management literature (eg,
407 Dainty and Millett, 2001; Briscoe and Dainty, 2005). The rationale behind the
408 requirement for cooperation and coordination is the importance of promoting timely
409 identification and communication of H&S risks for appropriate action, including
410 ensuring that everybody who needs to know of the risk has access to the relevant
411 information. It is part of the duties of the CDM Client, acting through the PD and the
412 PC, to take reasonable steps to ensure that the management systems and procedures for
413 the project adequately address the need for such cooperation and coordination.

414

415 A notable feature of the NEC family standard form contracts is that most of them
416 impose a contractual duty to give effect to the drafting policy of encouraging
417 cooperation throughout the project supply chain. For example, Clause 10.2 of the NEC4
418 ECC states that the Parties, the Project Manager and the Supervisor are to act in a “spirit
419 of mutual trust and co-operation”. To promote cooperation within the supply chain,
420 Clause 26.3 provides that the Project Manager’s rejection of the Contractor’s proposal
421 to appoint a sub-contractor would be valid if the reason for the rejection is that the sub-
422 contract does not include a term equivalent to Clause 10.2.

423

424 **6.5 Early Warning Procedures**

425

426 At the pre-contract stage of an NEC4 ECC project both parties are to list in their
427 respective sections of the Contract Data any early warning matter they are aware of at
428 that stage. An early warning matter (EWM) is defined in Clause 15.1 as: “any matter
429 which could: increase the total of the Prices; delay Completion; delay meeting a Key
430 Date or impair the performance of the works in use”. It is to be noted that the definition
431 is exhaustive; it covers matters which will affect Prices, progress or quality. H&S risk is
432 not mentioned specifically although some matters within the definition may also be
433 H&S risks. However, there is no contractual duty to notify H&S risks that will not
434 impact on Prices, delays and quality although such risks are likely to be rare.

435

436 The Project Manager is required by Clause 15.2 to draw up the first Early Warning
437 Register within a week of the “*starting date*”, which is the date entered in Contract Data
438 part one. Clause 11.2(8) defines “Early Warning Register” (EWR) as “a register of
439 matters which are: listed in the Contract Data for inclusion and notified by the Project
440 Manager or the Contractor as early warning matters”. Clause 15.1 puts a duty on the
441 Project Manager and the Contractor to notify each other of an EWM as soon as they
442 become aware of it. The Project Manager is to enter every matter so notified in the
443 EWR.

444

445 The mechanism for making decisions on a notified EWM is an early warning meeting.
446 It is a requirement of the contract that early warning meetings are held at regular
447 intervals. The maximum interval is required to be specified in the Contract Data. The
448 Project Manager is to instruct the Contractor to attend the first early warning meeting
449 within two weeks after the *starting date*. The Project Manager and Contractor may
450 instruct each other to attend an early warning meeting outside the scheduled meetings.

451 Such meetings are intended to deal with urgent matters that cannot wait until the next
452 scheduled meeting. Sub-contractors and others that can assist in decision-making or the
453 implementation of actions likely to be agreed at an early warning meeting must be
454 required to attend it (Clause 15.2).

455

456 The Project Manager and the Contractor may give each other early warning notice of
457 any matter that could increase the Contractor's total costs. Some may take a view that it
458 is not right for a Project Manager paid by the Client to divert any attention to the
459 Contractor's costs. However, such a view would be ignoring their Clause 10.2 duty of
460 mutual trust and cooperation and the fact that, in cost based contracts, such attention
461 would be directly in the Client's interest. The Project Manager would not be complying
462 with this duty if drawing the matter to the Contractor's attention would save the
463 Contractor costs. Such a view would also be losing sight of the reality that it is not in
464 the Client's interest for the Contractor to run into preventable financial difficulty.

465

466 **6.6 Risk Allocation Provisions**

467

468 Clause 81.1 identifies issues that are Contractor's liabilities. They include personal
469 injury suffered by the Contractor's employees, other people on the site or even members
470 of public. Most of these risks would involve breach by the Contractor of its CDM duties
471 or breaches by parties, such as sub-contractors, for whom the Contractor is responsible.

472 Clause 82.1 makes the Contractor liable for "any cost which the Client has paid or will
473 pay as a result" of any of the risks listed in Clause 81.1. Clause 80.1 lists risks for
474 which, as between the Client and the Contractor, the Client carries liability. Many of
475 these risks are likely to be the consequence of the Client's breach of duties under the

476 Regulations. The implication of the express reference to breach of statutory duty is that
477 the Client carries liability for personal injury caused by breach of the Regulations by the
478 Client or any other CDM duty holder (other than the Contractor) the Client contracts
479 with for the purposes of the works. Clause 82.2 provides for the Client to indemnify the
480 Contractor should the latter incur costs as a consequence of these risks.

481

482 **6.7 People with Appropriate H&S Competences**

483

484 The importance of CDM duty holders staffed by people with appropriate SKE is the
485 bedrock of the CDM 2015. This approach is consistent with the management paradigm
486 running through the NEC Contracts. The ECC anticipates entry of the following
487 information on *key persons* in the Contract Data part two for the project: name; job;
488 responsibilities; qualifications; and experience. To achieve this outcome, the Client
489 specifies the numbers and attributes of the relevant categories of *key persons* in the
490 Scope or the tender documents. Clause 24.1 puts the Contractor under an obligation to
491 provide the *key persons* so identified. Under Clause 24.2 any replacement of a *key*
492 *person* is subject to acceptance by the Project Manager. These features of the contract
493 can be applied to ensure the competence necessary for effective H&S management.
494 Clause 24.3 gives the Project Manager the power to instruct the contractor to remove
495 any person from the project, which power can be exercised to remove individuals whose
496 continued presence on the project could be detrimental to H&S.

497

498 **6.8 Payment linked Health Safety Performance**

499

500 The easiest way to incentivise compliance with the CDM 2015 is to have provisions
501 imposing such compliance as a condition precedent to the Project Manager certifying
502 achievement of Completion. Alternatively, as discussed under Section 6.1, Completion
503 can be defined in the Scope to include the achievement of specific H&S targets. Where
504 Option X16 applies, such provision holds up release of the retention until compliance.
505 In view of the low margins in the construction industry, the retention often exceeds the
506 contractor's entire profit from the project. Another option is to have items in the
507 contract prices for specified CDM or wider H&S targets that are included in payment
508 only when they have been achieved. A third possibility is to provide for a stated
509 percentage of the PWDD to be retained in the assessment of the amount due for
510 payment. Such provision would mirror Clause 50.5 which incentivizes submission of
511 the first programme.

512

513 **6.9 Contractor's Obligations in Respect of the Construction Phase Plan**

514

515 The ECC contract anticipates the entry of an *access date* in the Contract Data part one.
516 This is the date when the contractor may start work on site. Multiple *access dates* are
517 entered where different parts of the Site are available from different dates. Clause 30.1
518 provides that no work should start on site until the first *access date*. Regulation 4(5)(a)
519 requires the Client to ensure that a CPP is drawn up before the commencement of the
520 "construction phase", which is defined in the Regulations to mean the period for work
521 on site. As this constraint is not stated in the *conditions of contract*, it should be stated
522 in the Scope.

523

524 The requirement in Regulation 12(4) that the PC should ensure that the CPP is
525 reviewed, updated and revised from time to time throughout the duration of the project
526 implies that work on site may commence before it is complete. Most revisions of the
527 CPP are likely to be necessitated by changes to the Scope. It is also possible that a
528 change to the CPP necessitates a change to the Scope. No issue of compensation arises
529 where the PC is also the Contractor. However, there could be issues where these duty
530 holders are different. The express requirement for cooperation and coordination among
531 CDM duty holders and the Clause 10.2 duty to act in a spirit of mutual trust and co-
532 operation suggest that both changes are best made by discussion. As this type of
533 conduct cannot always be guaranteed, there is a case for putting a duty on the Project
534 Manager to issue an instruction implementing the necessary change to the Scope where
535 the PC is not also the main contractor. Such provision ensures that the contractor is
536 compensated for change to work content or methods priced for in the contractor's
537 tender.

538

539 **6.10 Early Contractor Involvement**

540

541 It is often argued that it would be impossible for the Client who uses the traditional
542 procurement approach to comply fully with the CDM Regulations. Secondary Option
543 X22 is designed to enable early contractor involvement in the design process at the pre-
544 construction stage.

545

546 **7 THE NEC4 PROFESSIONAL SERVICES CONTRACT**

547

548 Civil engineers deliver a wide range of professional services on construction and
549 engineering projects, The traditional services include: preliminary studies, surveys,
550 geotechnical investigations, design, project management, and contract administration
551 (Institution of Civil Engineers, 2015). The CDM Regulations have had the effect of
552 extending the range of services delivered by civil engineers to include the provision of
553 services as PD or PC. The Professional Services Contract (PSC) has been designed for
554 use in procuring these types of services. The documents making up a contract in this
555 form are: Form of Agreement, conditions of contract, Contract Data part one and two;
556 Prices/Activity Schedule; and Scope. These documents mirror their equivalents in the
557 NEC4 ECC in relation to their function. The composition of the package of services to
558 be delivered by a Consultant depends on the Client's decisions implementing its
559 procurement and contract strategies.

560

561 In conformity with the NEC policy on flexibility, the PSC does not prescribe the service
562 to be provided. That detail is to be provided in the Scope, which is not only to describe
563 the service to be delivered but also to identify any constraints to its delivery. According
564 to the accompanying User Guide (NEC, 2017e), information relevant to H&S to be
565 provided in the Scope include: existing information on the service to be delivered (eg,
566 PCI); project team; communication systems; management procedures; interfaces with
567 third parties; co-ordination and co-operation; H&S requirements; and programme
568 information. The PSC has been drafted with the traditional services of engineers in mind
569 although the current version is flexible enough to be also appropriate where the
570 Consultant is not only a designer but also a PD.

571

572 The nature of the role of designer or PD is one of delivery of professional services. The
573 duties in these roles may be provided as part of the much wider role of the traditional
574 Architect/Engineer as project lead on construction and engineering projects. On design
575 and build (D&B) projects, the PD may be the main contractor (with or without external
576 CDM advisors) or an independent design consultant. A PD must be appointed before
577 tendering for the appointment of the D&B contractor where the drawing up of the
578 Client's requirements entails design. The PD at this stage may be an independent design
579 consultant although a contractor may take on this role where there is early contractor
580 involvement.

581

582 Specialist H&S professionals not from these traditional professional backgrounds also
583 offer services as PDs. Where the PC role is provided by the main/prime contractor for
584 the project, the PC CDM role may be subsumed as part of the duties of the main
585 contractor under the main construction contract. However, it is possible for the PC role
586 to be undertaken by a professional in a similar way to architects and engineers acting as
587 professional construction managers where a project is being procured by the
588 construction management procurement route. Regulation 5(1) expects the PD to be
589 appointed in writing. A written appointment may be a simple letter offering the role and
590 its acceptance by the intended appointee. However, the appointment may be a formal
591 contract for professional services with detailed terms on the performance of the contract
592 by both parties.

593

594 As with its counter-part in the NEC4 ECC, the conditions of contract in the PSC
595 contract are the terms governing the details of the performance required of each party.
596 The only references in them to H&S are in Clauses 24.3, 31.2 and 91.3. The Consultant

597 has a duty under Clause 24.3 to “act in accordance with the health and safety
598 requirements stated in the Scope”. As a minimum, the Scope should state the obligation
599 of the Consultant to comply with any statute, statutory instrument, regulation or other
600 rule having the force of law relevant to the works or the performance of its other
601 obligations under the contract. The Consultant’s CDM duties as Designer or PD, as the
602 case may be, should also be stated. Finally, the specific tasks in the particular
603 assignment must be set out in the Scope for ease of enforcement. Clause 31 of the PSC
604 conditions of contract provides for programmes for delivery of the services of the
605 Consultant in terms that mirror the programming requirements of NEC4 ECC. Clause
606 31.2 requires the Consultant to indicate in any programme submitted to the Client
607 information on its arrangements for meeting the H&S requirements. Under Clause 91.3
608 the Client may terminate the contract for the Consultant’s substantial breach of “safety
609 regulation”, which includes the CDM Regulations.

610

611 As is common to most NEC contracts, the Consultant and the Client are to act “in spirit
612 of mutual trust and co-operation” (Clause 10.2). There is a wider duty on the Consultant
613 to co-operate with the Client and “Others”, which term is defined in Clause 11.2(7) as
614 “people or organisations who are not the Client, the Consultant, the Adjudicator or any
615 employee, Subconsultant or supplier of the Consultant.”. Others therefore include
616 designers, the PD, the PC and the Contractor where they are independent of the
617 Consultant.

618

619 The performance of the role of a CDM Client requires relevant skills, knowledge and
620 other professional resources. A Client without these attributes may consider appointing
621 an appropriate professional to perform the tasks within the statutory duty on its behalf.

622 Examples of tasks that can be performed by a professional on the Client's behalf
623 include: the preparation of the PCI; tendering for the appointment of duty holders; and
624 assessment of their SKE/OC. Such an arrangement does not transfer the criminal
625 liability risk but the prosecuted Client would have a cause of action for professional
626 negligence against its CDM Agent. Recoverable compensation in such action would
627 include legal costs of defending the criminal prosecution and damages for reputational
628 loss. An alternative arrangement is to extend the role of the PD to take over
629 performance of some of the duties of the Client.

630

631 The Professional Services Short Contract (PSSC) (NEC, 2017f) is an abridged version
632 of the PSC for smaller commissions. This form would be more appropriate than the PSC
633 where the Consultant is providing only PD services on a project. The documents making
634 a contract in the PSSC form are: Form of Agreement (Consultant's Offer and the Client's
635 Acceptance); Conditions of Contract, Contract Data, Price List; and Scope. The only
636 reference to H&S in the Conditions of Contract for the PSSC is in Clause 90.3, which
637 entitles the Client to terminate the Consultant's appointment for substantial breach of
638 H&S regulation. The Scope must therefore be comprehensive as to the service to be
639 provided, the programme for delivering it and the parties' rights and obligations in
640 relation to performance of the CDM role.

641

642 **8 DISCUSSION**

643

644 A shortcoming of prosecution of H&S offences is that it is reactive; by the time the
645 HSE gets involved, the impact on the Client may be unstoppable or may even have
646 occurred already. Also, the HSE has resources to exert such control over only a tiny
647 fraction of the projects that are ongoing at any given time. A more effective control
648 instrument is an appropriate contract with each of the duty holders which the Client can
649 use as a lever to enforce performance by its appointees.

650

651 The legislation does not identify in detail the actions that must be taken to comply with
652 the Regulations. Performance of such details can be imposed as contractual terms, thus
653 empowering the Client to enforce them before failures result in a breach of the statutory
654 duty. Furthermore, without detailed terms on what the duty holder must do to comply
655 with its duty, there could be divergence between the expectations of the duty holder and
656 those of the Client, thus producing conflict that can negatively affect the project. A
657 contractual relationship also offers the Client the opportunity to delegate, to appropriate
658 duty holders, some of the Client's practical procedures for compliance with its duties
659 under the Regulations. For example, the PD is only required to assist the Client with the
660 preparation of the PCI (Regulation 11(6)(a)). However, the Client and the PD may agree
661 in their contract that the PD not only prepares the information but also undertakes the
662 tasks necessary for producing it (eg, identification of surveys the Client must
663 commission to obtain the necessary information). The Client cannot however transfer
664 the risk of prosecution for failure to provide, to designers and contractors, PCI that is fit
665 for purpose.

666

667 The multiple level of sub-contracting raises issues concerning how the Client can
668 exert influence throughout the entire project supply chain. For example, the information
669 necessary for the HSF may be scattered across the supply chain. This reality raises
670 questions as to how to compel all sub-contractors at all levels to supply necessary
671 information in their possession to the PD. Enforcement throughout the entire supply
672 chain can be enabled through contracts that are back-to-back with each other in
673 relation to CDM duties. For example, the duty to supply the information must be in not
674 only the contract between the Client and the main contractor but also all sub-contracts.

675

676 Traditional construction contracts have provided for specific project participants, such
677 as the Client's Project Manager or Representative, Contract Administrator, Project
678 Quantity Surveyor, and Supervisor, with specific duties that must be performed for
679 proper contract management. The CDM Regulations introduce participants with H&S
680 hats. There can be confusion over the extent of a participant's role and the necessary
681 interaction with other participants or roles. An appropriate contract is the only way to
682 ensure embedment of the CDM procedures and duty holders into the general contract
683 management system.

684

685 Users of the NEC contracts need to pay particular attention to structuring the relevant
686 contract documents for consistency with the CDM documents. For example, much of
687 the contents of the PCI would belong to the categories of information that should be in
688 the Site Information contract document, e.g, structures on the site, and reports of subsoil
689 and other surveys. Duplication of some categories of information in the two documents
690 carries the risk of inconsistencies arising from failure to update both documents
691 contemporaneously. Keeping the common information in one document and making

692 references to it from the other is therefore to be preferred to duplication. Reference to
693 information in the PCI from the Site Information contract document suffers from the
694 disadvantage that, by its very nature, the PCI is a live document that must be revised to
695 update it for new information. It is also to be noted that it is not a contract document.
696 NEC guidance advises pointing from the PCI to factual information in the Site
697 information whilst avoiding the PCI straying into requirements and constraints, which
698 should be in the Scope. There are similar challenges with the CPP. The Contractor and
699 all tiers of sub-contractors are required by Regulation 15(3) to comply with the parts of
700 the CPP relevant to their work on the project. Change to the CPP made available to
701 bidders would have cascading impact on compensation events and associated
702 adjustment of rights and obligations with respect to payment and the timetable for
703 carrying out the works.

704

705 The conduct and culture that use of the NEC contract is intended to engender are
706 precisely the behaviours of cooperation and coordination that duty holders under the
707 Regulations are required to adopt in the management of H&S. Bolt *et al* (2012) found
708 that the contractual framework for the procurement of the built facilities for the 2012
709 London Olympic Games, which was based on NEC3 contracts, was a major contributor
710 to delivery of the projects with outstanding H&S outcomes. But mere use of the contract
711 by parties without buying into the NEC philosophy is unlikely to be the silver bullet for
712 leveraging good H&S outcomes. Not only must the Client exhibit these behaviours but
713 its assessment of the SKE/OC of candidates for appointment as duty holders or other
714 project participants must therefore take account of these factors.

715

716 The general approach of the NEC contracts is that the detailed CDM related obligations
717 are provided in the Scope. The terms concerning H&S in the conditions of contract
718 would be of limited effectiveness without clear statement of these details in the Scope.
719 The importance of getting the drafting of this document right cannot therefore be
720 overemphasised. This approach has the advantage of furthering the interests of the
721 publishers of the contracts in making them usable internationally whilst UK users of the
722 contract can draft the Scope to impose the CDM obligations as contractual
723 requirements. However, this approach to engaging with the CDM Regulations has the
724 shortcoming that it leaves too much to the competence of the drafter of the Scope.
725 Competence requirements of the drafter include: knowledge and understanding of the
726 Regulations; knowledge of the terms of the NEC4 contract to avoid inconsistency
727 between the Scope and the other contract documents; and competence in the NEC
728 drafting style.

729

730 Assuming possession of the necessary competences, there are a number of points the
731 drafter must still bear in mind in the drafting of the Scope:

- 732 • Copying out relevant provisions from the Regulations is likely to result in
733 provisions that are too general to be of much use for practical enforcement
734 purposes.
- 735 • As a change to information in the Scope is a compensation event (Clause 60.1(1)),
736 there is need for care not to include in the Scope matters that are subject to change
737 but for which the Client does not bear the risk.
- 738 • The legislation does not prescribe the content of the CDM documents. The Scope
739 would be the appropriate place in which to specify the types of information to be
740 provided and the templates for providing the documents.

741 • In line with the policy that Completion under the ECC should be defined in the
742 Scope, the definition should include a statement that Completion is not achieved
743 unless and until the Contractor has complied with specific CDM duties such as
744 provision of information necessary for the HSF.

745

746 As the competence of the drafter of the Scope for particular projects cannot always be
747 guaranteed, there is a strong case for standard provisions as part of the ECC conditions
748 of contract that reflect the reality that a Contractor with some responsibility for design
749 may be required to exercise concurrently the roles of not only a “contractor” under the
750 Regulations but also those of “designer”, “principal designer”, and “principal
751 contractor”. An appropriate alternative approach to implementing CDM related duties
752 into the ECC without detracting from the need for flexibility for international use would
753 be to have CDM related terms as a CDM Optional Clause (eg, as Option Y(UK) 4) that
754 UK users may adopt. The provisions in such an optional clause may include:

- 755 • the names and contact information of the PD and PC linked to entries for them in
756 the Contract Data;
- 757 • names of designated staff on the project;
- 758 • how duty holders or their designated staff on the project may be changed;
- 759 • the Parties’ obligations to comply with their respective obligations under the
760 Regulations;
- 761 • the Contractor’s duty not to start work on site before the CPP is drawn up;
- 762 • the Contractor’s obligation to comply with the CPP and to ensure that all sub-
763 contractors also do so;
- 764 • the parties’ mutual right to terminate the contract for significant breach of their
765 CDM obligations;

- 766 • the Contractor’s obligation to provide information for the HSF and ensure that all
767 sub-contractors do the same;
- 768 • the Project Manager’s power to withhold approval of sub-contractors under
769 Clause 26 if the sub-contract does not include appropriate terms on H&S; and
- 770 • the Project Manager’s duty to issue instructions to implement changes to the CPP
771 that impact on the Scope where the Contractor is not also the PC.

772

773 Some of the Client’s consultants on the project, such as the lead consultant and others
774 who prepared the documents for the project, may have legal duties at common law (for
775 example, see: *Townsend (Builders) Ltd v Cinema News & Property Management Ltd*
776 (1959) 20 BLR 118; *BL Holdings v Robert J Wood & Partners* (1979) 12 BLR 1;
777 *Pozzolanic Lytag Ltd v. Brian Hobson Associates*(1999) 15 Const. LJ 135) to advise the
778 Client on the adequacy and implications of the contractual provisions or the Client’s
779 need for such advice from appropriate experts (Furst and Ramsey, 2016; Dennys and
780 Clay, 2015; Speaight and Stone, 2010). These duties may apply to the need for
781 provisions in the Scope that adequately address obligations under the Regulations.

782

783 **9 CONCLUSIONS**

784

785 Although the HSE is the statutory enforcement authority for H&S legislation on
786 construction projects, it is arguable that the burden of enforcement of H&S must lie
787 more with the project owner who initiated the project. The most effective enforcement
788 instrument available to the Client, who has no powers of prosecution, is an appropriate
789 contractual relationship with each of the duty holders that imposes compliance with the

790 applicable CDM duties as contractual obligations. The approach of the NEC family of
791 contracts is to state in the conditions of contract document of the relevant contract a
792 general obligation to comply with H&S legislation, leaving the detailed requirements to
793 be captured in the Scope drafted for the particular project. UK users must therefore
794 ensure that the drafter of the Scope has the competence necessary to produce a
795 document in the NEC drafting style that adequately captures the specific H&S
796 obligations under the Regulations. Training in the drafting of the H&S section of the
797 Scope is an essential element of the current approach. Revision of the user guides to
798 provide more detailed guidance on the drafting of the CDM related content of the Scope
799 contract documents is recommended. An alternative approach to providing for the
800 CDM Regulations that the promoters of the NEC contracts may wish to consider having
801 a CDM Option for adoption by UK users.

802

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810

811 **CASE LAW**

812

813 *Arnold v Britton* [2015] UKSC 36.

814 *BL Holdings v Robert J Wood & Partners* (1979) 12 BLR 1.

815 *Chartbrook Ltd v Persimmon Homes Ltd* [2009] UKHL 38.
816 *Investors Compensation Scheme Ltd v West Bromwich Building Society* [1998] 1 WLR
817 896;
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820 *Pozzolanic Lytag Ltd v. Brian Hobson Associates* (1999) 15 Const LJ 135.
821 *Rainy Sky SA v Kookmin Bank* [2011] UKSC 50.
822 *Townsend (Builders) Ltd v Cinema News & Property Management Ltd* (1959) 20 BLR
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